

SQUARE DIMENSIONAL MEMBERSHIP FUNCTIONS OF SOFT STRUCTURES

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Abstract:

A new dimensional membership functions called square membership functions [SDMFSS] under soft set theory are defined in this article. Also we have studied arbitrary intersections, level membership functions and its subgroup structures with suitable examples.

Key Words: Membership Functions, Index Set, Arbitrary Set, Family of Square Functions & Subgroup Structures

1. Introduction:

The idea of bipolar valued fuzzy set was introduced by K.M.Lee [8, 9], as a generalization of the notion of fuzzy set. Since then, the theory of bipolar valued fuzzy sets has become a vigorous area of research in different disciplines such as algebraic structure, medical science, graph theory, decision making, machine theory and so on [2, 4, 6, 16,7]. Convexity plays a most useful role in the theory and applications of fuzzy sets. In the basic and classical paper [15], Zadeh paid special attention to the investigation of the convex fuzzy sets. Following the seminal work of Zadeh on the definition of a convex fuzzy set, Ammar and Metz defined another type of convex fuzzy sets in [1]. From then on, Zadeh's convex fuzzy sets were called quasi-convex fuzzy sets in order to avoid misunderstanding. Soft set theory was introduced by Molodtsov [13] for modeling vagueness and uncertainty and it has been received much attention since Maji et al [12], Ali et al [4] and Sezgin and Atagun [14] introduced and studied operations of soft sets. This theory has started to progress in the mean of algebraic structures, since Aktas, and Cagman [3] defined and studied soft groups. A new dimensional membership functions called square membership functions [SDMFSS] under soft set theory are defined in this article. Also we have studied arbitrary intersections, level membership functions and its subgroup structures with suitable examples.

2. Basic and Previous Concepts:

2.1 Definition [D. Molodtsov]: A pair (δ, A) is called a soft set over U , where δ is a mapping given by $\delta : A \rightarrow P(U)$. In other words, a soft set over U is a parameterized family of subsets of the universe U . Note that a soft set (δ, A) can be denoted by δ_A . In this case, when we define more than one soft set in some subsets A, B, C of parameters E , the soft sets will be denoted by $\delta_A, \delta_B, \delta_C$, respectively. On the other case, when we define more than one soft set in a subset A of the set of parameters E , the soft sets will be denoted by $\delta_A, \delta_{A'}, \lambda_A$, respectively.

2.2 Definition [M.I. Ali, F. Feng]: Let δ_A and Δ_B be two soft sets over U such that $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$. The restricted intersection of δ_A and Δ_B is denoted by $\delta_A \Psi \Delta_B$, and is defined as $\delta_A \Psi \Delta_B = (\lambda, C)$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $c \in C$, $\lambda(c) = \delta(c) \cap \Delta(c)$.

2.3 Definition [M.I. Ali, F. Feng]: Let δ_A and Δ_B be two soft sets over U such that $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$. The restricted union of δ_A and Δ_B is denoted by $\delta_A \cup_R \Delta_B$, and is defined as $\delta_A \cup_R \Delta_B = (\lambda, C)$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $c \in C$, $\lambda(c) = \delta(c) \cup \Delta(c)$.

2.4 Definition: Let δ_A be a SDMFSS over U . Then (M, N) -level of SDMFSS δ_A , denoted by $\delta_A^{(M, N)}$, is defined as follows $\delta_A^{(M, N)} = \{x \in A / \delta_A^P(x) \geq M \text{ and } \delta_A^N(x) \leq N\}$ for $M \cap N = \phi$.

Assume at if $M = \phi$ or $N = U$, then $\delta_A^{(\phi, U)} = \{x \in A / \delta_A^P(x) \neq \phi \text{ and } \delta_A^N(x) = U\}$ is called Support of δ_A , and denoted by $\text{Supp}(\delta_A)$.

2.5 Example: Let $D = \{d1, d2, d3, d4\}$ be an initial universe and $f = \{f1, f2, f3\}$ be a parameter set. If we define SDMFSS as follows

Then the positive membership functions are defined $\{f1, f3\}, \{f1, f2, f3\}$ and the negative membership functions are $\{f1, f2, f3, f1f2, f2f3\}$.

Let $M = \{f2, f3\}$ and $N = \{f2, f3, f1f2\}$. Then $\delta_A^{(M, N)} = \{f1f2\}$.

3. Some Standard Results (Propositions):

The following propositions are proved based on the definitions

3.1 Proposition:

Let δ_A and δ_B be two SDMFSS over U. $A, B \subseteq E$. Then following assertions hold(*)
 $\delta_A \subseteq \delta_B \Rightarrow \delta_A^{(M,N)} \subseteq \delta_B^{(M,N)}$, for all $M, N \subseteq U$ such that $M \cap N = \phi$.

(**) If $M_1 \subseteq M_2$ and $N_1 \subseteq N_2$, then $\delta_A^{(M_1, N_1)} \subseteq \delta_A^{(M_2, N_2)}$ for all $M_1, M_2, N_1, N_2 \in U$ such that $M_1 \cap N_1 = \otimes$ or $M_2 \cap N_2 = \otimes$.

(***) Some places are denoted M, N for alpha and beta notations.

(****) $\delta_A = \delta_B \Rightarrow \delta_A^{(\alpha, \beta)} = \delta_B^{(\alpha, \beta)}$, for all $\alpha, \beta \subseteq U$ such that $\alpha \cap \beta = \phi$.

Proof:

Let us assume that δ_A and δ_B be two SDMFSS over U.

*Let $x \in \delta_A^{(\alpha, \beta)}$, then $\delta_A^P(x) > \alpha$ and $\delta_A^N(x) \leq \beta$.

Since $\delta_A \subseteq \delta_B$, $\alpha \subseteq \delta_A^P(x) \subseteq \delta_B^P(x)$ and $\delta_A^N(x) \supseteq \delta_B^N(x) \supseteq \beta$ for all $x \in G$.

$\Rightarrow x \in \delta_B^{(\alpha, \beta)}$. Hence $\delta_A^{(\alpha, \beta)} \subseteq \delta_B^{(\alpha, \beta)}$.

**Let $\alpha_1 \subseteq \alpha_2$ and $\beta_1 \subseteq \beta_2$ and $x \in \delta_A^{(\alpha_2, \beta_2)}$, then $\delta_A^P(x) \geq \alpha_2$ and $\delta_A^N(x) \leq \beta_2$.

But we have $\alpha_1 \subseteq \alpha_2$ and $\beta_1 \subseteq \beta_2$, $\delta_A^P(x) \geq \alpha_1$ and $\delta_A^N(x) \leq \beta_1 \Rightarrow \delta_A^{(\alpha_2, \beta_2)} \subseteq \delta_A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1)}$.

****This case proved in a simple manner.

3.2 Proposition:

Assume that δ_A and δ_B be two SDMFSS over U. $A, B \subseteq E$ and $\alpha, \beta \subseteq E$ such that $\alpha \cap \beta = \phi$.

Then

(i) $\delta_A^{(\alpha, \beta)} \cup \delta_B^{(\alpha, \beta)} \subseteq (\delta_A \cup \delta_B)^{(\alpha, \beta)}$

(ii) $\delta_A^{(\alpha, \beta)} \cap \delta_B^{(\alpha, \beta)} \subseteq (\delta_A \cap \delta_B)^{(\alpha, \beta)}$

Proof:

(i) For all $x \in E$, let $x \in \delta_A^{(\alpha, \beta)} \cup \delta_B^{(\alpha, \beta)}$

$\Rightarrow (\delta_A^P(x) \geq \alpha \text{ and } \delta_A^N(x) \leq \beta) \vee (\delta_B^P(x) \geq \alpha \text{ and } \delta_B^N(x) \leq \beta)$

$\Rightarrow (\delta_A^P(x) \cup \delta_B^P(x) \geq \alpha) \text{ or } (\delta_A^N(x) \cap \delta_B^N(x) \leq \beta) \Rightarrow x \in (\delta_A \cup \delta_B)^{(\alpha, \beta)}$

Hence $\delta_A^{(\alpha, \beta)} \cup \delta_B^{(\alpha, \beta)} \subseteq (\delta_A \cup \delta_B)^{(\alpha, \beta)}$.

(ii) For all $x \in E$, let $x \in \delta_A^{(\alpha, \beta)} \cap \delta_B^{(\alpha, \beta)}$

$\Rightarrow (\delta_A^P(x) < \alpha \text{ and } \delta_A^N(x) > \beta) \vee (\delta_B^P(x) \geq \alpha \text{ and } \delta_B^N(x) \leq \beta)$

$\Rightarrow (\delta_A^P(x) \cup \delta_B^P(x) \geq \alpha) \text{ or } (\delta_A^N(x) \cap \delta_B^N(x) \leq \beta) \Rightarrow x \in (\delta_A \cup \delta_B)^{(\alpha, \beta)}$

Hence $\delta_A^{(\alpha, \beta)} \cap \delta_B^{(\alpha, \beta)} \subseteq (\delta_A \cap \delta_B)^{(\alpha, \beta)}$.

3.3 Propostion:

Let I be an index set and δ_A be a family of SDMFSS over U. Then, for any $\alpha, \beta \subseteq U$ such that $\alpha \cap \beta = \phi$,

(i) $\bigcup_{i \in I} (\delta_{A_i}^{(\alpha, \beta)}) \subseteq (\bigcup_{i \in I} \delta_{A_i})^{(\alpha, \beta)}$

(ii) $\bigcap_{i \in I} (\delta_{A_i}^{(\alpha, \beta)}) = (\bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_{A_i})^{(\alpha, \beta)}$

3.4 Proposition:

Let δ_A be a BSFS-sets over U and $\{\alpha_i / i \in I\}$ and $\{\beta_j / j \in I\}$ be two non-empty family of subsets of U. If $\alpha = \bigcap \{\alpha_i / i \in I\}$, $\bar{\alpha} = \bigcup \{\alpha_i / i \in I\}$, $\beta = \bigcap \{\beta_j / j \in I\}$ and $\bar{\beta} = \bigcup \{\beta_j / j \in I\}$, then the following assertions hold,

$$\bigcup_{i \in I} \delta_A^{(\alpha_i, \beta_j)} \subseteq \delta_A^{(\alpha, \bar{\beta})} \quad \bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_A^{(\alpha_i, \beta_j)} = \delta_A^{(\bar{\alpha}, \beta)}$$

3.5 Proposition:

Let δ_G be a SDMFS subgroup over U and $\alpha, \beta \subseteq U$ such that $\alpha \cap \beta = \phi$. Then $\delta_G^{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is also SDMFS-subgroup of G whenever it is non empty.

Proof:

It is clear that $\delta_G^{(\alpha, \beta)} \neq \phi$.

Suppose that $x, y \in \delta_G^{(\alpha, \beta)}$, then $\delta_G^P(x) \geq \alpha$, $\delta_G^P(y) \geq \alpha$ and $\delta_G^N(x) \leq \beta$, $\delta_G^N(y) \leq \beta$.

$$\inf \delta_G^P(xy^{-1}) \geq \min \{ \inf \delta_G^P(x), \inf \delta_G^P(y^{-1}) \} = \min \{ \inf \delta_G^P(x), \inf \delta_G^P(y) \}$$

$$\geq \min(\alpha, \alpha) \geq \alpha$$

$$\sup \delta_G^P(xy^{-1}) \geq \min \{ \sup \delta_G^P(x), \sup \delta_G^P(y^{-1}) \} = \min \{ \sup \delta_G^P(x), \sup \delta_G^P(y) \}$$

$$\geq \min(\alpha, \alpha) \geq \alpha$$

and

$$\inf \delta_G^N(xy^{-1}) \leq \max \{ \inf \delta_G^N(x), \inf \delta_G^N(y^{-1}) \} = \max \{ \inf \delta_G^N(x), \inf \delta_G^N(y) \}$$

$$\leq \max(\beta, \beta) \leq \beta$$

$$\sup \delta_G^N(xy^{-1}) \leq \max \{ \sup \delta_G^N(x), \sup \delta_G^N(y^{-1}) \} = \max \{ \sup \delta_G^N(x), \sup \delta_G^N(y) \}$$

$\leq \max(\beta, \beta) \leq \beta$. Therefore, we have $xy^{-1} \in \delta_G^{(\alpha, \beta)}$ and $\delta_G^{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a SDMFS subgroup of G .

3.6 Proposition:

Let δ_{G_i} be a family of SDMFS-subgroup over U for all $i \in I$. Then $\bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}$ is a SDMFS -subgroup over U .

Proof:

Let $x, y \in G$. Since δ_{G_i} be a SDMFS-subgroup over U for all $i \in I$. This shows that

$$\delta_{G_i}^P(xy^{-1}) \geq \min \{ \delta_{G_i}^P(x), \delta_{G_i}^P(y) \} \text{ for all } i \in I. \text{ Then}$$

$$\inf \delta_{G_i}^P(xy^{-1}) \geq \min \{ \inf \delta_{G_i}^P(x), \inf \delta_{G_i}^P(y) \}$$

$$\inf \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^P(xy^{-1}) \right) \geq \bigcap_{i \in I} \min \{ \inf \delta_{G_i}^P(x), \inf \delta_{G_i}^P(y) \}$$

$$= \min \left\{ \inf \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^P(x) \right), \inf \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^P(y) \right) \right\} \text{ and}$$

$$\sup \delta_{G_i}^P(xy^{-1}) \geq \min \{ \sup \delta_{G_i}^P(x), \sup \delta_{G_i}^P(y) \}$$

$$\sup \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^P(xy^{-1}) \right) \geq \bigcap_{i \in I} \min \{ \sup \delta_{G_i}^P(x), \sup \delta_{G_i}^P(y) \}$$

$$= \min \left\{ \sup \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^P(x) \right), \sup \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^P(y) \right) \right\} = \min \{ \sup \delta_{G_i}^P(x), \sup \delta_{G_i}^P(y) \}$$

$$\text{and } \inf \delta_{G_i}^N(xy^{-1}) \leq \max \{ \inf \delta_{G_i}^N(x), \inf \delta_{G_i}^N(y) \}$$

$$\inf \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^N(xy^{-1}) \right) \leq \bigcup_{i \in I} \max \{ \inf \delta_{G_i}^N(x), \inf \delta_{G_i}^N(y) \}$$

$$= \max \left\{ \inf \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^N(x) \right), \inf \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^N(y) \right) \right\}$$

$$\text{and } \sup \delta_{G_i}^N(xy^{-1}) \leq \max \{ \sup \delta_{G_i}^N(x), \sup \delta_{G_i}^N(y) \}$$

$$\sup \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^N(xy^{-1}) \right) \leq \bigcup_{i \in I} \max \{ \sup \delta_{G_i}^N(x), \sup \delta_{G_i}^N(y) \}$$

$$= \max \left\{ \sup \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^N(x) \right), \sup \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i}^N(y) \right) \right\}. \text{ Thus } \bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_{G_i} \text{ is a SDMFS -subgroup over } U.$$

3.7 Proposition:

Let δ_G be a SDMFS-subgroup over U. Then $\delta_G(x^n) \geq \delta_G(x)$ for all $x \in G$ where $n \in N$.

Proof:

Suppose that δ_G is a SDMFS-subgroup over U. Then

$$\delta_G^P(x^n) \geq \delta_G^P(x) \cap \delta_G^P(x) \cap \dots \cap \delta_G^P(x)$$

$$\therefore \inf(\delta_G^P(x^n)) \geq \min\{\inf(\delta_G^P(x)), \inf(\delta_G^P(x)), \dots, \inf(\delta_G^P(x))\}$$

and

$$\delta_G^N(x^n) \leq \delta_G^N(x) \cup \delta_G^N(x) \cup \dots \cup \delta_G^N(x)$$

$$\therefore \inf(\delta_G^N(x^n)) \leq \max\{\inf(\delta_G^N(x)), \inf(\delta_G^N(x)), \dots, \inf(\delta_G^N(x))\}$$

Similarly

$$\sup(\delta_G^P(x^n)) \geq \min\{\sup(\delta_G^P(x)), \sup(\delta_G^P(x)), \dots, \sup(\delta_G^P(x))\}$$

$$\sup(\delta_G^N(x^n)) \leq \max\{\sup(\delta_G^N(x)), \sup(\delta_G^N(x)), \dots, \sup(\delta_G^N(x))\}$$
 and for all $x \in G$.

Thus $\delta_G(x^n) \geq \delta_G(x)$.

3.8 Proposition:

Let δ_G be a SDMFS-subgroup over U. If for all $x, y \in G$,

$$\inf(\delta_G^P(xy^{-1})) = U \text{ and } \inf(\delta_G^N(xy^{-1})) = \phi \text{ and } \sup(\delta_G^P(xy^{-1})) = U \text{ and } \sup(\delta_G^N(xy^{-1})) = \phi$$

Then $\inf \delta_G^P(x) = \inf \delta_G^P(y)$ and $\sup \delta_G^N(x) = \sup \delta_G^N(y)$.

Proof:

For any $x, y \in G$

$$\inf(\delta_G^P(x)) = \inf(\delta_G^P(xy^{-1}y)) \geq \min\{\inf \delta_G^P(xy^{-1}), \inf \delta_G^P(y)\} = \min\{U, \inf \delta_G^P(y)\}$$

$$= \inf \delta_G^P(y)$$

$$\text{And } \inf(\delta_G^P(y)) = \inf(\delta_G^P(y^{-1})) = \inf(\delta_G^P(x^{-1}(xy^{-1}))) \geq \min\{\inf \delta_G^P(x^{-1}), \inf \delta_G^P(xy^{-1})\}$$

$$= \min\{\inf \delta_G^P(x^{-1}), U\} = \inf \delta_G^P(x). \text{ Thus } \inf \delta_G^P(x) = \inf \delta_G^P(y). \text{ Also}$$

$$\sup(\delta_G^N(x)) = \sup(\delta_G^N(xy^{-1}y)) \leq \max\{\sup \delta_G^N(xy^{-1}), \sup \delta_G^N(y)\} = \max\{\phi, \sup \delta_G^N(y)\}$$

$$= \sup \delta_G^N(y) \text{ and}$$

$$\sup(\delta_G^N(y)) = \sup(\delta_G^N(y^{-1})) = \sup(\delta_G^N(x^{-1}(xy^{-1}))) \leq \max\{\sup \delta_G^N(x^{-1}), \sup \delta_G^N(xy^{-1})\}$$

$$= \max\{\sup \delta_G^N(x^{-1}), \phi\} = \sup \delta_G^N(x). \text{ Thus } \sup \delta_G^N(x) = \sup \delta_G^N(y).$$

Conclusion:

In this paper, we have to characterize the new membership function which is very useful for artificial intelligence and traffic signal problems.

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